

Taking Advice or “Sticking to Their Guns?”: Future Policymakers’ Consideration of Expert Advice in Policy Scenario Exercises

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Abstract

Understanding how policymakers use expert advice is important for promoting evidence-based policy decisions. But how does the next generation of leaders and policymakers consider expert advice? Using a sample of 18 first-year undergraduates enrolled in the Bachelor of Arts in Politics and Governance program and three graduate students from the Master of Arts in Political Science and International Affairs program at the American University of Armenia, this study examines whether students consider advice from experts when making hypothetical policy decisions in the Armenian context. This particular group of students was selected for study given their expressed interest in the field of public decision-making. Using carefully constructed policy scenario exercises, participants were first surveyed about their opinions on key policy topics, then exposed to written advice from experts and non-experts on these topics and asked to make hypothetical policy decisions. Participants were then asked to explain how they reached their chosen policy decision to determine whether the expert advice was considered. Focus groups were also conducted to gain insights into participants’ decision-making processes and their attitudes toward experts and expert advice in general. Results show that participants did not often consider expert advice when making policy decisions, especially when the expert-recommended course of action did not match their personal beliefs, and that expert advice was not an important part of participants’ decision-making process. Participants focused on normative concerns and value judgments, balancing between policy priorities, development of their country, and pragmatism when making hypothetical policy decisions. Understanding students’ current level of trust toward expert advice gives important insight into how future generations may approach the policymaking process. Results may also identify opportunities to strengthen students’ consideration and incorporation of expert advice in matters of policy and governance.

Keywords: experts, expert advice, policymakers, trust, policy decisions

Introduction

Given the increasing complexity of global, transdisciplinary, and long-term policy issues, policy decision making has become an increasingly complex

process (Dente, 2013). Recent crises from the COVID-19 pandemic to climate change to economic recessions have reinforced the importance of evidence-driven and expert-informed policymaking. Yet, expert advice is just one of the many inputs that policymakers must consider when making decisions; public sentiment, private and civil society sector priorities, budgetary constraints, feasibility, as well as their personal beliefs, party priorities, and concerns for their political careers may also influence policy decisions. Given these competing demands, what weight is given to expert advice in policy decision making?

Understanding the role that expert advice plays in policymaking is a prerequisite to devising ways to increase the use of evidence and expert advice in the policy process. In Armenia, a developing democracy with many unique challenges, the issue of policy formation is all the more salient. This research seeks to shed light on the role of expert advice in individuals' policy decision-making by using hypothetical policy decision scenarios with a unique population: future policymakers. By testing whether undergraduate and graduate students with a demonstrated interest in politics and governance consider expert advice when making policy decisions, we hope to gain a better understanding of how expert advice may be employed in Armenia's policy future.

Review of Previous Literature. Decision Making and Expert Advice

A wide body of research, primarily from the field of psychology, suggests that people discount advice when making decisions of any type (Sniezek & van Swol, 2005; Harvey & Fischer, 1997; Xiuxin & Xiufang, 2018; Yaniv & Kleinberger, 2000). Two principal explanations have been given for this phenomenon: that people under-adjust to advice by anchoring in their initial position (Harvey & Fischer, 1997), or that they rely on their own reasoning because they have access to it, whereas they do not have access to the reasoning of others (Yaniv & Kleinberger, 2000). Despite this general resistance, some evidence does suggest that when presented with advice from "novices" and "experts," people were slightly more likely to take advice from "experts" (Sniezek & van Swol, 2005; Xiuxin & Xiufang, 2018).

Several factors are thought to mediate the consideration of expert advice in decision-making. Sniezek and van Swol (2005) and Xiuxin and Xiufang (2018) found that people are more likely to consider expert advice when they have limited information about the topic or are less confident in their knowledge of a subject. Sniezek and van Swol (2005) also found that simply being assigned the role of a "judge" (decision maker) may make people more confident in their own judgment and less likely to take advice. The type of decision-making task may also be significant; Zarnoth and Sniezek (1997) found that participants in their decision making exper-

iments were more inclined to consider expert advice for intellectual tasks (tasks for which there is a right or wrong answer) than for judgmentive tasks (for which there is no objectively right or wrong answer). This last finding may be particularly relevant to policymaking, which is largely a judgmentive task.

One of the primary factors influencing whether decision makers consider expert advice is trust. Sniezek and van Swol (2005) found that trust in the advisor and the advisor's confidence in their advice are factors that affect whether someone uses expert advice in judging tasks. The advisor's confidence has also been found to be a significant factor affecting advisee's level of trust (Sniezek & van Swol, 2005; Xiuxin & Xiufang, 2018). Mayer et al. (1995) conclude that trust is built on perceptions of the ability, benevolence, and integrity of the advisor. Trust has also been found to be influenced by perceptions of the advisors' intentions (affect-based trust) and expertise (cognition-based trust) (McAllister, 1995; Bonaccio & Dalal, 2010; Xiuxin Wang & Xiufang Du, 2018).

When it comes to making policy decisions in particular, current research also points to the idea that policy makers' consideration of expert advice is mediated by political considerations (King, 2016; Dente, 2013; Lundin & Öberg, 2014; Boswell, 2005; Moore & Mackenzie, 2020; O'Shea & Ueda, 2021; Williams, 2001, Baekkeskov, 2016). Moore and Mackenzie (2020), discuss the often one-sided use of expert advice in policymaking, arguing that the consideration of expert advice creates a dynamic in which policymakers either hide behind expert advice or dismiss it as politically motivated, depending on how closely it matches their political beliefs. Dente (2013) concludes that research and scientific evidence are often used simply to justify decisions that have already been made. Boswell (2005) refers to this as expert advice's "substantiating function," which serves to legitimize politicians' or political parties' actions and policy positions rather than to provide objective, informed input. This function is especially prominent when a policy problem is perceived as having a high degree of risk. Lundin and Öberg (2014) also found that administrators were more likely to use expert advice to make policy recommendations to politicians for issues where there is a lot of public attention or disagreement, but noted that in these same situations politicians were less likely to deliberate over and use such expert advice. Several authors have also discussed the use of expert advice by policymakers to avoid blame (Baekkeskov, 2016).

Trust in expertise has been on the decline in recent years (Nichols, 2017). In a recent study focusing on COVID-19 and climate change policy, Geiger (2022) confirmed earlier findings that although experts are perceived as having higher expertise, they are considered only equally as trustworthy as non-experts; thus, expertise does not make someone more

trustworthy. These findings support the notion that because many policy decisions have normative dimensions necessitating value judgments in addition to scientific considerations, people have more trust in their own value judgments and priorities and those of the people closest to them (Geiger, 2022). An innovative online survey experiment conducted by O'Shea and Ueda (2021) also showed this politicization of expert advice based on personal values. In a survey of 1,875 Americans, they found that some groups are more likely than others to support those who ignore expert advice and attribute this to the fact that people are more likely to consider expert advice on political issues from those that they feel represent their values (Williams, 2001). The decline of trust in expertise may also partially be due to the general politicization of science and expertise in recent years. Nichols (2017) notes a growing hostility toward established knowledge and a glorification of ignorance as an assertion of autonomy. Some have suggested that the public's loss of faith in expertise stems from the fact that experts claim to be impartial while actually supporting certain political agendas, and that science is sometimes perceived as a tool for advancing these agendas (King, 2016).

While trust in expertise is an important factor to study, we must not lose sight of the end result—whether the advice of experts is actually acted upon. This is what Bennett (2020) refers to as “recommendation trust”—the willingness of people to not only trust experts but to further act on the recommendations experts advise (p. 244). Bennett's recommendation trust refers to the citizen-expert relationship, yet questions remain about how political decision-makers may experience this phenomenon. The current research seeks to investigate whether this “recommendation trust” is present in making policy decisions for a particular group of the Armenian population: potential future policymakers. Given the trends of discounting advice in general and the politicization of expert advice in particular, it is worth wondering what the future of evidence-based decision-making in Armenia may be. Through a series of realistic policy decision-making exercises, this research seeks to understand the extent to which expert advice influences participants' decisions in a policy scenario exercise by addressing the following research questions:

RQ1: How likely are future policymakers to select an expert-recommended course of action on a policy issue?

RQ2: How likely are future policymakers to select an expert-recommended policy option when their personal position on a policy issue differs from the position recommended by an expert?

RQ3: How do future policymakers explain their policy decisions?

Knowing how likely this population is to incorporate expert advice into their decision-making processes may help us understand the current

perception of expert advice among Armenia's next generation of policy-makers and possibly design interventions that will lead to increased consideration of such advice in the policy-making process in Armenia.

Methods

To investigate the questions above, a series of policy scenario exercises was conducted with 21 students with a demonstrated interest in policy and politics. All participants were enrolled in either the Bachelor of Arts in Politics and Governance program (BAPG; 18 participants) or the Master of Political Science and International Affairs program (PSIA; three participants) at the American University of Armenia. Eight of the participants were male and 13 were female. This particular group of students was selected to represent "future policymakers" because they have self-selected into academic programs that prepare them for roles in policymaking and public decision-making, and thus can be considered as some of the most likely and the most qualified individuals to occupy these positions in the future.

The BAPG program is also new—as it launched in Fall 2021, the participants were all in their first year of study at the time of their participation. Participants from the PSIA program were all also in their first year of study at the graduate level. Engaging students at this point in their academic careers provides a natural opportunity to study those who have an interest in policymaking but little formal training or experience. This also provides an opportunity to study the decision-making process of those who do not yet have concerns for their political careers, as this is believed to be an important mediating factor in many policy decisions (King, 2016).

The students were invited to participate in this study via program-wide emails and in-person invitations from instructors during regular class time. Participation in the study was completely voluntary and no compensation was offered. The survey was group-administered in paper form in three separate rounds on April 26, April 29, and May 10, 2022. No personal identifying information was collected, and therefore all responses are anonymous. Participants were informed that the purpose of the research was to study their policy decision-making processes. They were not explicitly informed that the focus of the research was the consideration of expert advice. This limited deception was necessary to avoid responses being influenced by social desirability bias. Participants were debriefed and informed of the full research purpose during follow-up focus groups, described below.

Policy scenario exercises like the one used in this study have been used in many situations as a tool for understanding and developing policy decision-making strategies (Toth, 1988; Wright, Stall, & Hatzakis, 2020;

Geiger, 2022). The policy scenarios exercise used here contained two major sections: personal policy positions and policy decision scenarios. In the first section, participants were asked to provide their personal positions by indicating the extent to which they disagree/agree (using a five-point Likert-style scale) with a series of 10 paired statements, representing opposing positions on five key policy issues related to the economy, health, education, the environment, and international relations. These responses were collected in order to evaluate whether participants moved from their initial positions in response to expert advice (or other factors) in the second section of the exercise.

In the second section, participants were presented with five realistic policy scenarios corresponding to the policy issues presented in the first section and were asked to make a decision from the perspective of a policymaker. The scenarios were developed to mirror real-life, current, local policy issues in Armenia. Scenario 1 was related to the issue of taxes, Scenario 2 to COVID-19 vaccinations, Scenario 3 to mining and environmental issues, Scenario 4 to education, and Scenario 5 to foreign relations. After being presented with a short description of the given issue and the context surrounding it, several quotes were given, representing viewpoints and recommendations of different members of the community. Each scenario included quotes from an individual clearly labeled as an “expert” as well as non-experts (members of the public, private sector representatives, clergy, politicians, etc.). Wherever possible, real advice from experts and non-experts were included to make the scenarios as realistic as possible. Participants were then directed to choose one option from a list of possible courses of action to address the policy issue. For each scenario, one option represents the course of action recommended by the expert. Each scenario also contained an open-ended question where participants were asked to explain their decision and the factors that influenced their decision-making process.¹

To better understand participants’ attitudes toward expert advice, two semi-structured debrief focus groups were conducted after the completion of the policy scenarios exercise. Fifteen BAPG students attended an in-person focus group held on May 18, 2022, and all three PSIA student participants attended a virtual focus group (conducted via Zoom) held on May 30, 2022. Participants were informed that the exercise intended to evaluate the extent to which expert advice played a role in their decision-making and were then invited to share their thoughts about their decision-making process during the policy scenario exercises and their thoughts on expert advice in general. The sessions were audio-recorded.

¹ The full policy scenarios exercise is available from the authors upon request.

Results

RQs 1 and 2: Choosing expert-recommended course of action and movement from personal policy position

A simple count was performed to determine the number of overall respondents who selected the expert-recommended course of action during the policy decision scenarios exercise. In all 105 decisions made during the exercise (five decisions each for 21 participants), there were 37 (35.2%) cases in which a respondent selected the expert-recommended course of action, and only 11 cases (10.4%) in which a participant chose a policy option that matched the expert's recommendation when the expert's position did not align with their personal policy position (moved from their initial policy position). The number of participants who moved from their initial position was greatest for Scenario 1, which concerned economic issues, and smallest for Scenarios 2, 3 and 4, which concerned COVID-19 vaccination, mining, and education, respectively.

Figure 1

Count (and percentage) of respondents whose personal policy position agreed with the expert recommendation; respondents who chose the expert-recommended policy option; and the number of respondents who chose the expert-recommended policy option when it did not match their personal policy position

Scenario	Number (%) of respondents who chose the expert-recommended policy option	Number (%) of respondents whose personal policy position matched the expert-recommended course of action	Number (%) of respondents who chose the expert-recommended policy option when it did not match their personal policy position	Number (%) of respondents who did not choose the expert-recommended policy option when it matched their personal policy position
1- Taxes	14 (66.6%)	12 (57.1%)	5 (23.8%)	3 (14.2%)
2- COVID-19	5 (23.8%)	8 (38%)	1 (4.7%)	4 (19%)
3- Mining	9 (42.8%)	20 (95.2%)	0	0 ²
4- Education	3 (14.2%)	12 (57.1%)	1 (4.7%)	1 (4.7%)
5- International relations	4 (19%)	1 (4.7%)	3 (14.2%)	0
TOTAL	37 (35.2%)	53 (50.4%)	10 (9.5%)	17 (16.1%)

In fact, a greater number of respondents (22.85%) actually moved away from the expert-recommended policy action when their initial position showed agreement with the expert's recommendation. Possible reasons for these trends are discussed in the discussion and conclusion section.²

RQ3: Factors Influencing Policy Decisions

To better understand the factors that influenced participants' decisions in the policy decision scenarios, qualitative analysis was performed on two key data sources: the responses to the open-ended questions following each policy decision scenario, and focus group transcripts. Two reviewers independently analyzed the data by hand to identify key categories and themes using an inductive approach. These key themes were then compared and consolidated to create two coding schemes (one for the open-ended responses and one for the focus group transcript). Each reviewer then coded the data a second time using the finalized coding schemes. Results of this coding showed a high-degree of inter-coder agreement (about 92%).

Key themes that emerged from this analysis include participants' focus on normative judgments/personal beliefs, development concerns, and pragmatic considerations in their decision-making strategies. Participants also displayed and described attempts to "balance" between competing priorities by choosing a path that would satisfy the greatest number of parties. Participants in the focus group also expressed skepticism toward experts and expert advice.

The following tables show the frequency of the key themes in the analysis of open-ended question responses and focus groups, respectively. There are some themes common to both sets of data, but there are also themes unique to each. Texts were coded thematically, and a single unit of text could be coded as representing more than one theme.

Figure 2

Description and frequency of key themes from analysis of open-ended question responses in policy decision scenarios

Theme	Description	Frequency
Normative/ Personal beliefs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participants explained their decisions in normative terms. - Reasoning was based on what is "right" or "wrong," according to their personal moral code or belief system. - References to rights or "human rights" (e.g., "Forcing people to get vaccinated is a human rights violation." / "Everyone should have the right to..."). - Statements about the "correct" role of people or institutions (e.g., "It is the job of the government to..."). - Mentions of fairness (e.g., "It is not fair to..."). 	48

² Because of the way that Scenario 3 was constructed, there were 11 respondents whose initial position agreed with the expert and who did not choose the expert-recommended policy option but are not said to have moved away from their initial policy position, because the option they chose was still in line with their initial position. This is because there were two options that could be considered in agreement with Statement 5 in the initial policy positions section.

Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participants' explanations for their decisions were mainly framed in terms of concerns about Armenia's economic development and advancement. - Participants mentioned that a certain course of action was chosen because it was considered good for the country. - Decision was based on what Armenia "needs." 	43
Balancing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participants' explanations of their decisions show that they considered multiple perspectives/options and trade-offs (e.g., "This is good, but..."). - Responses indicated an effort to satisfy as many groups as possible. - Participants tried to create the most favorable, centrist outcome. - Participants considered the outcomes or people's reactions to a certain policy decision. 	34
Pragmatic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decisions were based on whether a given option was practical, feasible, possible, or likely to be successful. - Participants mentioned that they would choose/not choose a certain option because it would/would not work. 	9

Figure 3
Description and frequency of key themes from analysis of focus group transcripts

Theme	Description	Frequency
Normative/ Personal beliefs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participants expressed that they made choices in the policy decision exercise based on their current personal beliefs, experiences, or values. - Participants noted that they rejected advice that did not match their personal beliefs, regardless of the source of that advice. - Responses suggested a tendency to seek options that confirmed or matched their personal beliefs. 	17
Balancing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A participant mentioned that when completing the policy decisions exercise they tried to choose an option that provided the most favorable outcome for the greatest number of groups. - Their explanations reflected an effort to evaluate trade-offs between different perspectives and options. - Participants tried to look for the optimal solution. - They tried to take multiple perspectives into account when making a decision. 	14

<p>Skepticism toward experts</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participants explicitly mentioned that they believed experts are not trustworthy or that advice from experts is not reliable. - They expressed the view that experts are biased/subjective/"human" and push their own political perspectives or the perspectives of their funders when giving advice. - Participants stated that advice from experts is not important because experts do not have special or more reliable information. - The credibility of the term "expert" was questioned as participants noted that many people claim to be experts but are not. - Experts were perceived unreliable because they are removed from the "real," everyday context. -Participants mentioned that the term "expert" is abstract and does not automatically inspire trust; trust must be earned through knowledge of a particular expert's credentials and experience. 	<p>10</p>
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Each of these key themes is briefly described in more detail below, with examples.

Normative concerns and personal beliefs. Most often, participants justified their decisions in the policy scenario exercises with reference to their own opinions and personal beliefs about what is good, proper, fair, just, and right—they focused on normative concerns. This was the main theme present in the open-ended responses (occurring 48 times) and the most common view expressed in the focus group (occurring 17 times). Participants seemed mostly concerned with what they felt personally was the right or moral thing to do, without mention of or deference to expertise. In relation to Scenario 1, regarding taxes, one participant exemplified this theme by writing, "Raising taxes on all (corporations and individuals) would be unfair towards the more vulnerable factions of the population" (Participant 5, Scenario 1). Although the participant chose the expert-recommended course of action, they justified this choice based on personal ideas of fairness, rather than the more scientific arguments put forth by the expert. This theme also showed up as a strong appeal to the language of rights and human rights. For example, in relation to Scenario 2, in which an expert recommended mandatory COVID-19 vaccinations for high-contact workers, one participant wrote that, "making people to get vaccinated is a violation of their rights" (Participant 6, Scenario 2), while another wrote that, "in my opinion, forcing others to get vaccinated is a violence" (Participant 9, Scenario 2). There was also reference to the correct role of government, as when one participant justified a policy decision by writing, "a government should support its rural citizens and those students have a right to get quality education as citizens of Armenia" (Participant 8, Scenario 4).

This theme was strongly echoed in the focus group, where it was the

most common explanation participants gave for their policy choices. One participant explained:

Most of the time, I completely disregarded the expert advice because this was, like, full-on voting along party lines—like, along the ideological lines that I believe in. So, you know, if the expert opinion just happens to coincide with mine, yeah, okay, cool (focus group participant).

Many participants explained that they often ignored any advice received and instead skipped straight to the policy choices, selecting the option that most closely aligned with their personal views. “I was not specifically looking at whose suggestions [they] were, like, expert or an ordinary citizen—I was just looking whether this point of view corresponds with mine. So my decision-making was mainly based on that,” said one participant.

Development concerns. Participants’ written responses to the open-ended questions from the policy decision scenarios often focused on the economic or developmental benefits that the chosen course of action would have for Armenia. This was often favored over other concerns or the arguments raised by the expert or other parties’ viewpoints given in the scenarios, such as concern for the environment, health, or long-term consequences. For example, in deciding whether to accept a proposed trade deal with China given certain trade-offs regarding human rights, one participant explained, “Armenia is not in a position where they can afford to be extremely picky with foreign investors” (Participant 5, Scenario 5). In the same scenario, another participant conveyed concern for development even more strongly, writing that Armenia should seek assistance from wherever it is available, “even if it is from Satan himself.” They wrote, “Everything, at any cost, should be done in the interests of the Republic of Armenia and the Armenian nation and in protection of the Republic of Artsakh” (Participant 12, Scenario 5).

This theme was unique to the open-ended question responses—participants did not mention their utilization of this strategy during the focus group session.

Balancing. Many participants showed attempts to balance between competing perspectives and priorities, weighing the different options in their explanations of their choices in the policy decision scenarios. “Even though it creates discrimination toward students living in cities, a quota system might be a success as many students living in rural communities are skilled and intelligent but do not have enough opportunities,” wrote one participant when explaining their policy choice on Scenario 4 (Participant 7). Often, participants displayed attempts to balance between the two other main themes—their personal values/opinions and economic/development priorities. A typical example comes from a participant who justified a policy choice by writing: Being a member of a society means

that you have a responsibility towards your community. So getting vaccinated is from the altruism perspective. Since Armenia's economy is based on services, the lower [the] number of people getting vaccinated, the [greater the] likelihood of lockdown which severely affects the country's economy (Participant 19, Scenario 2).

In their responses to the open-ended items on the policy decision scenarios exercise, participants frequently mentioned a few of the perspectives offered by different parties. For example, regarding the mining situation in Scenario 3, one participant wrote, "as it is crucial for creating local jobs, for the development of the country it is better to use the given chance but pay attention and follow all the necessary norms of keeping environmental risks" (Participant 21, Scenario 3), reflecting perspectives of the expert as well as a business owner who recommended a different policy option.

Participants also spoke of their attempts to engage this balancing strategy in the focus group. One participant explained:

I really did not, like, take the expert advice or value it way more than the other advice. I tried to make all of them into one thing and think about—for example, the taxes. The expert suggested increasing corporate taxes only. But there was another suggestion that [suggested raising] corporate taxes and, like, all taxes in general, which in my opinion was less discriminatory and it was equal treatment to everyone; it doesn't matter your income. And for me that was more valuable than the expert advice. And so I just kind of tried to lump them all into one together and tried to fit into what I believe in and what they said. (Focus group participant)

Participants often chose the option that they felt would be the most acceptable to the greatest number of parties or would create a more centrist outcome. For example, one focus group participant said:

For me, it was how I think politically about a certain situation and then I evaluated every single opinion, every piece of advice that was given to me... I kind of tried to manage the conflicting interests, the conflicting ideas of the expert and my own beliefs... to make all parties satisfied. (Focus group participant)

Pragmatic. For some participants, their selection of a certain policy option was based on the perceived feasibility or practicality of that option. This was sometimes framed around the public's reaction to or expected compliance with a certain policy option. One respondent explained their choice of a particular policy option by saying, "honestly, I want to choose the first option. However, it would create many problems and many people would protest against the government" (Participant 11, Scenario 2). In another example, a participant chose a certain policy option based on how

efficiently it uses resources by writing, “I don’t think convincing anti-vaxxers to change their views is worth the resources spent, especially during the pandemic. I would re-allocate those funds to hospitals and economic aid” (Participant 11, Scenario 2).

Skepticism about experts’ motives and credibility. The focus group revealed that many participants harbor outright skepticism for experts and expert advice. The main reasons given for this skepticism were that experts are human beings and therefore are not neutral. As one participant mentioned, “even if you are an expert, how can you be neutral? You’re still a human being with thoughts and beliefs. Even when it comes to politics, I’m sure they have a bias.” Many further argued that experts are funded by external parties that use the research to push their own agendas. Some even questioned the idea that experts do have privileged knowledge, or suggested that experts should only be trusted on very technical or scientific topics. One participant explained: “So, in that sense, if it was a physics expert telling me that this rocket will not fly, I’ll be like, ‘yep, this rocket will not fly,’ but if it’s economics or politics expert that’s saying that we should do x to y, like, yeah, I don’t know...” Some participants mentioned that experts may not have the most reliable information because they are often removed from the real-life, “on-the-ground” situation.

Participants also mentioned that their skepticism toward experts stems partially from not having enough information about the experts themselves. As one participant illustrated:

When we say experts without, let’s say, giving a face to the expert, it really becomes, let’s say, an abstract idea. And if it was, let’s say, a person, you know, we know he’s very—achieved a lot of things, very accomplished, and that person suggested this or that solution, then I think we’ll be more inclined to listen to the experts. (Focus group participant)

Others echoed this sentiment, explaining that they did not know anything about that particular expert’s credentials, background, experience, and potential conflicts of interest and so exercised some caution when it came to taking the expert’s advice simply on the basis of the fact that they were labeled as an “expert.”

As participants were not aware of the specific focus on expert advice when completing the policy decision scenarios exercise, this theme was not present in the responses to the open-ended questions on that exercise.

Discussion and Conclusion

The results of this study suggest that these “future Armenian policymakers” are unlikely to take advice from experts when making policy deci-

sions, particularly when the course of action recommended by an expert does not align with their personal positions on a given issue. The findings further suggest that expert advice is not a significant factor in the decision-making processes of this particular group. The most influential factors in their policy decisions were their personal beliefs, judgments, and experiences, followed by concerns for national development, and pragmatism. Participants also demonstrated efforts to balance between multiple policy priorities and expressed skepticism toward experts and their advice. Thus, the results above indicate that, currently, Armenia's future policymakers are more likely to "stick to their guns" rather than defer to experts when making policy decisions.

Overall, these findings are consistent with previous literature. As van Swol and Snizek (2005), along with others (Harvey & Fischer, 1997; Xiuxin & Xiufang, 2018; Yaniv & Kleinberger, 2000) also found, participants in this study discounted advice when making decisions and instead anchored in their initial judgments. This is most clearly seen in the participants' explanations of their decisions in the policy decision scenarios, which most often focused on their personal value judgments. This disregard for expert advice and strong skepticism toward experts expressed in the focus group session may reflect the current trend of eschewing expert advice as an "badge of cultural sophistication" (Nichols, 2017, p. 21). It could also be related to one of many factors that are proposed to mediate trust.

Interestingly, participants did not exercise the proposed "substantiating function" of expert advice. Even when their policy decisions matched the course of action recommended by an expert, the advice of experts was not used to bolster their explanations of that policy choice. This is most clearly seen in the fact that many participants did not choose the expert's recommendation even when it matched their personal policy position. This may have to do with the way the scenarios were presented, indicating that participants' support for a certain policy position depends on the situation to which it applies. Alternatively, this could be further evidence of the employment of the "balancing" strategy, with advice from other parties outweighing that of experts. Another interpretation is that there is a strong skepticism toward experts, which leads participants to reject an option that they would otherwise support simply because it was associated with an "expert." Overall, there seems to be both low trust in experts and their advice and a lack of "recommendation trust" (Bennett, 2020) when making policy decisions.

It is interesting to note that in the policy decision scenarios, the expert course of action was most frequently chosen in the scenario related to economic or tax issues. This may be due to the perceived complexity of economic issues relative to other issues (environment, health, education), or to the extent that economic policy is viewed as a more "technical,"

intellective task rather than a judgment-based one. This may suggest that the willingness to use expert advice in policy decisions may increase for this group as the perceived complexity of the task increases.

A few limitations of this study must be addressed. While the results reveal some intriguing initial patterns, the small sample size makes it impossible to generalize to all those who would be considered “future policymakers” in Armenia. Different patterns may emerge among those from other disciplines, attending other schools, or not receiving any formal education. Further, the study cannot predict how future policymakers may evolve between now and the time when they actually move into policy decision-making positions. Most importantly, the study does not offer definitive conclusions about current policymakers’ feelings about expert advice or use of expert advice in policy decision-making. In order to reach more generalizable conclusions, this study could be expanded or replicated to include a larger sample of the population of “future policymakers” or to allow for comparison between future and current policymakers. In order to capture more detail in the policy scenario exercises, the exercise could test explicitly the differences in the likelihood of taking advice between different types of policy scenarios. Future research could also investigate further the factors that shape skepticism toward experts and expert advice.

One additional outcome of this research is the development of tools such as the one used here to study and develop policy decision-making. Given that this study employed an experimental, non-standard tool developed specifically for this exercise, the reliability and validity of the results are not guaranteed. The construction of the scenarios and the advice from different parties may have affected participants’ decisions and their considerations of expert advice; thus we cannot fully isolate the effect of expert advice. One potential improvement for the tool would be asking participants to choose one of a pair of dichotomous statements to indicate their personal policy preferences, as this would better allow for comparisons with the responses in the policy decision scenario exercise than Likert-type responses. However, in the focus group session, participants expressed that they found the exercise very useful for thinking through policy issues and exercising their decision-making abilities. They also mentioned that, after learning the true purpose of the research study, they felt that the tool did adequately capture their decision-making strategies. This type of exercise may be useful as an educational tool in students’ coursework to further develop practical decision-making skills. Similar exercises could also be adapted for use with current policymakers.

A primary advantage of studying this particular population is the possibility to design interventions that can potentially increase the use of expert advice in future policy decisions. Based on the results above, a number of recommendations have been developed to supplement the ed-

ucation of these future policymakers. First, given that the primary factors that participants relied on to make their policy decisions were personal value judgments and balancing between competing priorities, courses in ethics are paramount for expanding and developing future policymakers' normative reasoning. Exposure to a range of ethical perspectives and dilemmas can help them develop their ability to consider multiple perspectives when making decisions for the public good. Such courses could also include discussion of the meaning of expertise and improve reasoning and argumentation based on critical thinking about the theories, values, and ethics of decision-making. Extending and reinforcing the series of research methods courses is also recommended to build a greater appreciation for the rigor and credibility of empirical research conducted by experts, which will lead to a better understanding of the criteria for judging expertise and expert knowledge. Finally, courses on the policy process will help build a more nuanced understanding of the role that expert advice can play relative to other considerations. These recommendations will help to support these future policymakers in considering evidence-based policy recommendations that will bring informed policy choices for Armenia's future prosperity.

Focus group participants' expressed lack of trust in experts further suggests that additional steps must be taken to raise the perceived value and credibility of experts and expert advice. Given that many expressed skepticism on the grounds that "experts are human beings" who may carry their own personal biases and that their credentials were unknown, perhaps creating opportunities for policymakers to learn more about experts themselves would raise the level of trust in experts' advice. Further research should be conducted to examine whether having more information about an expert's background (and identifying what information in particular) will increase the level of consideration of and trust in expert advice.

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